

ARCHITECTURE AND ARCHITECTURAL TERMS. TRANSLATING ARCHITECTURAL TERMS: PECULIARITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: *This article focuses on the main peculiarities and challenges of architectural terms as well as the great importance of architectural terms in simultaneous translation. Additionally, some main reasons such as effective communication, facilitating collaboration, enhancing learning and education, ensuring cultural sensitivity, expanding market opportunities, and fostering diversity and inclusivity, plays a vital role in promoting translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation.*

Keywords: *architecture, architectural terms, effective communication, architectural knowledge, collaboration, diversity, professional development.*

Today, architectural domain are accelerating rapidly in our country. At the same time, new terms and expressions are emerging into the Uzbek language from foreign languages related to the fields of construction engineering and architecture. Sometimes we can use an alternative version of such terms in our language, and sometimes we have to use the term itself, which is not an alternative. Therefore, in order to find a solution to such problems, the wide use of world information resources is one of the urgent tasks.

In the studies carried out in our country on the further development and improvement of the state language, it is still observed that the terms related to the construction industry are used in Russian, and they are also taught in Russian even in educational institutions. This trend creates difficulties for our future professionals. It is clear that we need to make many reforms in many areas for the development of our language. Although some terms have equivalents in Uzbek, they are still used in Russian, for example, the term "apka" is still used as "apka" despite being translated as "ravoq" in Uzbek. This indicates that the literature in this field is mainly in Russian, or not everyone knows that there is an alternative version in Uzbek.

Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation refers to the process of conveying architectural concepts, terminology, and technical jargon from one

language to another in real-time during an architectural event, conference, or presentation. Simultaneous translation involves an interpreter listening to the speaker's words and rendering them into the target language simultaneously.

In the context of the architecture this requires a deep understanding of architectural terminology, design principles, construction techniques, and cultural nuances to accurately convey the speaker's intended meaning to the audience. Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation plays a crucial role in facilitating effective communication and knowledge exchange among professionals in the field of architecture, allowing architects, engineers, and stakeholders from different linguistic backgrounds to engage in meaningful discussions and collaborate on international projects.

Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation is a complex task that requires expertise in :

- ***language proficiency ;***
- ***architectural knowledge;***

Architectural terms often involve specific terminology related to building materials, construction techniques, design principles, and spatial concepts. The interpreter must possess a deep understanding of these terms in both the source and target languages to accurately convey the intended meaning to the audience.

During simultaneous translation, the interpreter listens to the speaker's words through headphones and immediately translates them into the target languages, speaking into a microphone. The translated message is then transmitted to the audience, allowing them to follow the presentation in their preferred language in real-time. To effectively translate architectural terms, interpreters rely on their background knowledge of architecture, extensive research, and preparation. They familiarize themselves with architectural terminology in both languages and stay up-to-date with current industry trends. It is essential for interpreters to understand the specific context in which architectural terms are used, such as architectural styles, urban planning concepts, or sustainability practices

Furthermore, interpreters must adapt their translations to suit the cultural and linguistic nuances of the target audience. They need to consider regional variations in architectural terminology and ensure that their translations are accurate, clear, and culturally appropriate.

Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation is a specialized skill that requires a combination of language proficiency, architectural knowledge, and cultural sensitivity. By effectively conveying architectural. By effectively conveying architectural concepts across language barriers, interpreters play a vital role in

facilitating global communication and collaboration within the architecture field. Based on my experience, translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation is of great importance for several reasons:

1)Effective Communication:

Architecture is a global field, and professionals from different countries and linguistic backgrounds often collaborate on projects or attend conferences and events. Translating architectural terms allows individuals to understand and engage in meaningful discussions, ensuring effective communication and knowledge exchange.

2)Facilitating Collaboration:

International architectural projects involve teams from various countries, including architects, engineers, contractors, and clients. Accurate translation of architectural terms ensures that all team members can understand and contribute to the project, promoting collaboration and synergy among diverse professionals.

3)Enhancing learning and Education:

Architectural conferences, seminars, and workshops provide valuable learning opportunities. Translating architectural terms enables participants to fully comprehend and absorb the knowledge shared by speaker's, regardless of their native language. This promotes professional development and the dissemination of architectural expertise across different regions.

4)Cultural Sensitivity:

Architecture is deeply intertwined with culture, and specific terminologies may carry cultural significance or reflect local practices. Translating architectural terms with cultural sensitivity ensures that the intended meaning and context are preserved, avoiding misinterpretations or misunderstandings that may arise from a literal translation.

5)Market expansion:

Translating architectural terms facilitates the internationalization of architectural firms, enabling them to engage with clients and stakeholders from diverse linguistic backgrounds. By breaking down language barriers, firms can expand their reach, attract international projects, and compete in global markets.

6)Promoting diversity and Inclusivity:

Architecture thrives on diverse perspectives and influences. By translating architectural terms, professionals from different language communities can actively participate in discussions, contributing their unique insights and enriching the architectural discourse with a broader range of perspectives.

¹ The human brain loves a challenge, but only if it is within an optimal zone of difficulty. If you love tennis and try to play a serious match against a four-year-old, you will quickly become bored. It is too easy. You will every point. In contrast, if you play a professional tennis player like Roger Federer or Serena Williams, you will quickly lose motivation because the match is too difficult. Now consider playing tennis against someone who is your equal. As the game progress, you win a few points and lose a few. You have a good chance of winning, but only if you really try, Your focus narrows, distractions fade away, and you find yourself fully invested in the task at hand.

This trend perfectly matches with interpreting process. If you are required to interpret common conversation, without any hesitation, you will have ability to translate it from source language to target one with few effort and less empirical knowledge. To put it into another perspective, supposing you may have to translate terms and jargons, abundance of knowledge of any field and experience are demanded so as to achieve clarity and coherence as well as to get high standard translation.

The main peculiarities of translating architectural terms encompass:

- *technical and specialized nature;*
- *cultural and historical connotations;*
- *visual and sensory aspects;*
- *linguistic diversity;*
- *modern and ancient terminology;*
- *legal and regulatory considerations;*

Briefly, translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation plays a vital role in promoting effective communication, facilitating collaboration, enhancing learning and education, ensuring cultural sensitivity, expanding market opportunities, and fostering diversity and inclusivity. Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation is a specialized skill that requires a combination of language proficiency, architectural knowledge, and cultural sensitivity. By effectively conveying architectural. By effectively conveying architectural concepts across language barriers, interpreters play a vital role in facilitating global communication and collaboration within the architecture field.

UNESCO declared Khiva's Ichan-Kal'a ensemble, Shakhriyabz city, the center of Bukhara and Samarkand's architectural monuments as world humanitarian values introduced to the world that Uzbekistan's architecture domain has been

¹ Atomic habits by James Clear page 231

developed since ancient times. Therefore, the interest in these humanitarian values is increasing sharply in the world today, and developed countries are expressing their desire to invest in the restoration¹. Even the most skilled translator, who has many years of experience in the term translation process, faces challenges. As mentioned above, one of the major problems in translation is that the same equivalent does not occur in different languages. The translator therefore tries to find an alternative to the term using different translation methods. In the Russian dictionary of construction terms compiled by DV Artyukhovich, the word "Khachish" has the following meaning: a building for guests, erected inside a special fence, away from the traditional manor. The word was borrowed from Kabardian in Russian, as the translator used the transliteration method because no word meaning this was found in Russian. We will focus on the following construction terms: Shaber / Scraper. In Russian and English, the Uzbek translation of these terms is a scraper - a tool for scraping and smoothing the surface of metal objects. But as a construction term, this word cannot fully express the meaning of the term construction. Therefore, we recommend that the Russian term shaber be translated into Uzbek by the method of transliteration. In the process of analyzing the original and translated variants of the text, we can observe that the translation of terms used mainly transliteration, transcription and syntactic methods. The disadvantage of the texts is that it can be understood only by a narrow segment of the population.²

References:

- 1) Atomic habits by James Clear page 231
- 2) Nozima Ikramovna Gafurova. "PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF CONSTRUCTION TERMINOLOGY" .CENTRAL ASIAN ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ISSN: 2181-2489 VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 6 | 2022
- 3) Samigov N.A. 2002.38

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² Nozima Ikramovna Gafurova. "PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF CONSTRUCTION TERMINOLOGY" .CENTRAL ASIAN ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ISSN: 2181-2489 VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 6 | 2022